

THE REACTION OF GREEN PEAS TO ENVIRONMENTAL FACTORS

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Annotation. Green peas are lightly absorbed into the body, rich in protein, which are mainly divided into combable and sugary forms consumed with their domes. Legumes are mainly used in liquid food, and green peas are used in the canned industry, tailoring meat, fish and vegetable food. It differs from the fact that other peas can also be consumed freshly and used frozen.

Keywords. Green peas, varieties, temperature, humidity, light, legumes.

Log in. Vegetable goroxi or green pea (*Pisum sativum* L.) contains very rich vitamins A, S, Group B and PP, which is vitamin B two times more than solid wheat, vitamin B2 is one and a half times more and vitamin PP five times more. 100 grams of peas contain 0.30-0.54 mg of carotene, vitamins K-0,28, B1-0,28, B2-0,15, PP-2,10, B6-0,18, S-20-59 milligrams.

Green peas also contain active lipotropic antiscotic substances, which play a major role in the body's conversion of fluids. Due to the high level of choline, green peas and its legumes have an anti-sclerosis effect and are characterized by the removal of radionuclides from the body, preventing the growth of harmful tumors. It helps to treat cardiovascular, liver, kidney disease, is recommended for patients with stomach and twenties of intestinal ulcers.

Green peas, which in nutrition hold one of the leading positions among vegetable crops, are 20-26 percent dry matter and contain 5-7 percent protein, 6-9 percent sugar, 1-3 percent starch, 6-7 percent fat and 2-6 percent crocodiles. Its nutritional coloria is 1.5-2.0 times higher than potatoes and other vegetables.

The purpose of the study. It is about studying the reaction of green peas to environmental factors.

Object of the study: Samples of blue peas from ICARDA.

Research methods: The placement of experiments was carried out on the basis of a methodological manual adopted by the State Commission for testing of agricultural crop varieties. Based on the methods developed by the Russian Institute of Plant Research named after N.I.Vavilov (1984), the State Testing Commission for Agricultural Crops of Uzbekistan (1985-1989) and the Samarkand branch of the Tashkent State Agrarian Unverstiti.

Results of the study: We studied the reaction of green peas to environmental factors in an experiment. The best past plants for green peas are roots, cabbages, tomatoes, and potatoes from wheat crops and vegetable crops processed between the rows. For green peas, strongly damaged land with grain crops, fields that have been empty of perennial crops and weeds is considered unsuitable. Weed leads to a 50-55% decrease in pea yield.

Attitude to temperature. Green peas are more frost-resistant than other vegetables, and their seeds begin to grow at a temperature of 2-3 degrees Fahrenheit [-3°C] and develop

well. The temperature of 8-12 degrees is considered favorable for the growth of green peas. When the air harrorat exceeds 32 degrees, the development of the plant slows down.

Attitude to lighting. Green peas are a long day's germ, and on bright and cool days we observed the acceleration of the development of the plant.

Attitude to nutritional elements. The root of green peas is 25-30% of the total plant content. Since its root system is located mainly at a depth of 35-40 cm in the soil, vegetable peas are very demanding to the soil fertility and mechanical composition. The green pea itself absorbs 50-55% of the nitrogen absorbed from the air. However, for its roots to develop enough, it is initially required to be given a nitrogen fertilizer of 30 kg/h. Molybdenum and the bor wealth as catalyst for the acceleration of nitrogen fixation. The feeding norm varies depending on the expected amount of crops.

The reaction of green peas to nutrient elements

	N ₂	P ₂ O ₅	K ₂ O
1 T/ga	30-35	15-20	10-55
5 T/ga	100	70-80	40-50
6 T//ga	120	100	70-80
7 T/ga	140	110	90-100

The reaction of green peas to moisture. Green peas love moisture compared to other diced crops. When planting peas in early spring, field wet capacity should not be less than 70-75%. The higher the humidity of the soil, the more the seeds grow uniformly. Lack of moisture in the soil and rising air temperature in such a vart causes the seeds to become moldy. The plant becomes more demanding for moisture during the period of diving, flowering and wax ripening.

References:

- 1.D.T.Abdukarimov, "Qishloq xo'jalik ekinlari seleksiyasi va urug'chiligi" Toshkent.2002
- 2.Amanova M.E, Xudoyorova X. Yashil no`xatning (p.Sativum L.Partim) ahamiyati va yetishtirish bo`yicha tavsiyalar, 2020.
- 3."Dukkakli ekinlar jahon kolleksiyasini o`rganish"bo`yicha uslubiy qo`llanma. (Lelingrad, 1976).
- 4.O`zbekiston Respublikasi hududida ekish uchun tavsiya etilgan qishloq xo'jalik ekinlari Davlat reestri, 2018.